

Ascent

Active storage of captured CO₂ in net zero
construction products

ASCENT

**Research protocols for different advanced
characterization techniques in LATOM**

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1 INTRODUCTION

The performance and durability of cementitious materials depend strongly on their chemical composition, physical characteristics, and interaction with their environment. To evaluate these properties, a variety of analytical and experimental techniques are employed, each providing unique insights into material behavior.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP), Blaine analysis, X-ray diffraction (XRD), calcimetry measurement with de Bernard method, chloride content determination, conductivity, and pH measurements are widely used methods for investigating the chemical stability, pore structure, and hydration characteristics of cement-based systems. Complementary techniques such as isothermal calorimetry and the Reactivity test (R3 test) allow the assessment of hydration kinetics and the intrinsic reactivity of supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs). Together, these advanced methods provide a comprehensive toolkit for understanding cement hydration, pore development, durability-related parameters (e.g., chloride ingress), and reactivity potential. Such data are critical for evaluation of newly developed formulation such as low-carbon binders, novel supplementary cementitious materials, and alternative binder chemistries. They also enable design of concrete with enhanced performance, longevity, and sustainability.

The following protocols outline the background and principles, equipment requirements, safety considerations, reagents, detailed procedures, reporting guidelines, and references for each method available in the LATOM laboratory. They intend to serve as a practical laboratory guide for consistent and reliable measurement of cementitious materials' properties.

Research protocols that have been provided in this report are reliable basis for the standardization of laboratory work. By ensuring that the same method is applied and verified across different laboratories, these protocols promote comparability and reproducibility of results. Standardized protocols also support the unified presentation of data, making dissemination and interpretation clearer for both researchers and industry stakeholders. The use of validated protocols enhances efficiency, improves the quality of output, and ensures uniform performance, while at the same time reducing the risk of miscommunication and non-compliance with industry regulations. In this way, validated protocols play a crucial role in advancing scientific collaboration and ensuring consistent application of analytical techniques. Since many advanced characterization methods are not yet standardised, this joint and simultaneous testing is essential to validate in-house results and strengthen the credibility and reliability of each participating laboratory. These protocols will be made publicly available, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and wider dissemination within the scientific community, especially among the Widening countries.

Within the LATOM laboratory, protocol management and instrument booking procedures have been systematically organised to ensure safe, consistent, and high-quality operation of all characterization equipment. For each device, individual protocol manuals have been prepared and placed next to the corresponding instrument (e.g., TGA, MIP, pH meter, etc.). These manuals contain step-by-step measurement procedures, safety instructions, sample preparation guidelines, troubleshooting notes, and documentation requirements. In addition, a central protocol book has been created to serve as a unified reference guide for all LATOM laboratory users, supporting standardisation and traceability of measurements.

Figure 1. Individual protocol manuals have been prepared and placed next to the corresponding instrument

Instrument booking is currently managed through a Google Calendar system, where trained and authorised faculty staff can reserve time slots for the use of specific equipment. This ensures transparent scheduling, prevents overlaps, and helps track instrument utilisation and maintenance needs. Only personnel who have completed the required training are granted access to the booking system and permitted to operate the instruments.

Figure 2. Screenshot of Google calendar system

Furthermore, regular maintenance checks, calibration routines, and logbook entries are required for each device to guarantee proper functioning and data reliability. This structured approach supports efficient laboratory management, promotes safe working practices, and enhances the overall quality of research outputs within the LATOM facility.

2 SAFETY, WASTE AND ORGANISATIONAL MEASURES

During any operations within the LATOM laboratory, strict safety precautions must be followed. Laboratory personnel must wear appropriate personal protective equipment, including a lab coat, safety goggles, chemical-resistant gloves, and, when handling powders, a dust mask or respirator. Strong acids such as hydrochloric (HCl), nitric (HNO₃), or hydrofluoric acid (HF), as well as strong alkalis like sodium hydroxide (NaOH) or potassium hydroxide (KOH), are commonly used in digestion procedures and must always be handled in a fume hood to prevent harmful exposure. Silver nitrate (AgNO₃), barium salts, and other heavy-metal solutions used in some wet chemical methods are hazardous and should be handled carefully to avoid skin contact. In addition, compressed gases used in systems must be properly secured and regularly checked for leaks.

Within the LATOM laboratory, a guideline document titled “Internal Instructions for Safe Laboratory Work” has also been developed. This manual provides detailed instructions on the correct handling of chemicals, the use and availability of personal protective equipment (PPE), and procedures for the safe storage and disposal of laboratory waste. It also includes guidelines for emergency response, incident reporting, ventilation and fume hood use, and safe operation of high-temperature and high-pressure equipment.

The document serves as a mandatory reference for all laboratory users and supports the establishment of a safe working environment by ensuring that safety practices are consistently followed. Regular safety briefings and periodic updates of the manual help maintain compliance with institutional and regulatory requirements, while also promoting a culture of responsibility and awareness within the LATOM facility.

Figure 3. LATOM laboratory guideline document titled “Internal Instructions for Safe Laboratory Work”

All waste generated during chemical analysis must be collected and disposed of according to institutional protocols. Acidic and alkaline solutions should be collected in separate, clearly labeled waste containers, while silver-containing solutions must be treated as hazardous waste. Solid residues from grinding or digestion must also be stored safely until proper disposal. To avoid cross-contamination and ensure reproducibility, laboratory workspaces should be kept clean and organized at all times. Instruments such as XRF, XRD, TGA, Blaine, calorimetry and MIP must be calibrated and maintained regularly. Finally, all samples, solutions, and calibration standards must be clearly labeled, and all measurement conditions and results should be documented systematically in a laboratory notebook or digital database.

Figure 4. Collection of waste materials – mercury contaminated waste

3 SAMPLE PREPARATION

Accurate determination of the properties of cementitious materials requires careful and standardized sample preparation. Representative samples of cement, supplementary cementitious materials, or hardened concrete should be collected according to relevant standards (such as EN 196 or ASTM C) and handled to avoid contamination with dust, aggregates, or environmental materials.

3.1 Drying of powdered materials

Before analysis, samples of powdered materials should be dried at 105 ± 5 °C to remove free moisture. Alternatively, 60 ± 5 °C for at least 24 h should be used when preparing sensitive samples with possible dehydration and microstructural changes at lower temperatures.

Once dried, the samples must be finely ground in a ball mill, planetary mill, or mortar grinder to achieve a uniform particle size. Homogenization of the powder is essential to ensure that the analyzed portion is representative of the whole. The preparation also depends on the analytical technique: for XRF, pressed pellets or fused glass beads are prepared to obtain accurate oxide quantification; for XRD, finely ground powders must be packed carefully to minimize preferred orientation effects; for TGA, small quantities of sample (10–50 mg) are weighed into crucibles. In wet chemical titrations, extracts are prepared by acid leaching with hydrochloric acid (HCl) followed by filtration.

3.2 Hydration Stoppage

Ideally, hydrated or hardened materials should be tested immediately after a certain age has been met. But, due to the equipment limitations a hydration stoppage method is unavoidable prior to testing. For cementitious systems, solvent exchange using isopropanol is a widely accepted and effective approach for stopping hydration while minimizing microstructural alteration.

A) Standard procedure

1. Submerge the sample in a glass container filled with 2-propanol ($\approx 2 \times$ sample volume).
2. Replace the solvent after 1 hour.
3. If the solution is still cloudy or slurry-like, replace the solvent again after 8 hours.
4. Continue soaking until the solvent appears clear.
 - Note for samples < 1 day old: Keep submerged for ~ 24 hours total.
 - Note for samples > 1 day old: Keep submerged for 5–7 days to ensure full hydration stoppage.
5. After solvent exchange is complete, remove the sample, place it in a partially open labeled bag, and transfer it to the vacuum chamber for low-temperature drying.

B) Hydrated cement paste for TGA measurement

1. Work in a fume cabinet to avoid exposure to dust and solvent fumes.
2. Crush and quickly grind the cement paste using a mortar and pestle
3. Mix ~ 5 g of the ground sample with 50 mL isopropanol in a glass beaker.
 - Let the suspension rest for 10–15 minutes to replace pore solution water.

4. Filter the suspension (e.g., using a Büchner funnel with aspirator pump) to remove excess isopropanol.
5. Wash the solid on the filter with 5–10 mL diethyl ether to remove residual isopropanol, and continue pumping until the sample lightens or pressure rises.
6. Dry the solid using one of the following options:
 - Spread on a petri dish and dry 8–10 minutes at 40°C in an aerated oven, or
 - Place in a vacuum desiccator for 1 h, or
 - Dry to constant mass in the TG under N₂ with no preheating.
7. Analyse immediately or the same day if possible.
 - Alternatively, store for a few days in a sealed container or under light vacuum.

References

Scrivener, K., Snellings, R., & Lothenbach, B. (2016). *A Practical Guide to Microstructural Analysis of Cementitious Materials*. CRC Press.

3.3 Sample storage

Prepared samples should always be stored in **vacuum desiccators** or inside a **nitrogen-filled chamber** (for long term storage) to prevent carbonation and the absorption of atmospheric moisture, both of which can alter their chemical composition. Alternatively, less sensitive materials may be stored in airtight containers. All containers must be clearly labelled with the sample identification.

All containers must be clearly labeled with the sample identification, date of preparation, and intended method of analysis. This ensures that the integrity of the samples is preserved and that results from different laboratories and methods remain comparable.

Figure 5. Vacuum desiccator and nitrogen-filled cabinet

4 CHEMICAL AND MINERALOGICAL COMPOSITION

Several analytical techniques are routinely applied to determine the chemical and mineralogical composition of cementitious materials: TGA, XRD, chloride content determination, conductivity, and pH measurements. Together, these methods provide a comprehensive picture of both the bulk chemical composition and the mineralogical/phase composition of cementitious systems, which are key to linking material chemistry with hydration, microstructure, and durability performance.

4.1 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Background and principle

X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a non-destructive analytical technique used to determine the crystalline structure, phase composition, and crystallite size of materials. When monochromatic X-rays interact with a crystalline solid, they are diffracted at specific angles according to Bragg's Law:

$$n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta$$

where n is the order of reflection, λ is the wavelength of incident X-rays, d is the interplanar spacing, and θ is the diffraction angle.

By scanning over a range of angles (2θ), a diffraction pattern is produced. Each crystalline phase generates a unique "fingerprint" of peaks, which can be compared to reference databases (e.g., ICDD PDF-4+) to identify phases and determine relative amounts. Peak broadening can be analyzed for crystallite size (via the Scherrer equation) and microstrain.

Special equipment

1. **X-ray diffractometer**, consisting of: X-ray source (commonly Cu $K\alpha$, $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$; or Co, Mo sources), goniometer for controlling incident and diffracted angles, sample stage (flat plate, capillary, or environmental chamber), detector (scintillation counter, solid-state, or strip detector).
2. **Sample preparation tools**: mortar and pestle, micronizing mill, glass slides, sample holders.
3. **Reference standards** e.g. silicon powder for instrument calibration.
4. **Computer with XRD analysis software** e.g., HighScore, Jade, TOPAS.
5. **Cooling and shielding systems** for the X-ray tube.

Chemical safety

XRD systems generate ionizing radiation; improper exposure can cause severe injury. Instruments must have interlocked radiation shielding. Never bypass safety interlocks. Only trained personnel should operate the diffractometer. X-ray tubes operate at 20–60 kV. Ensure power is off during maintenance. Fine powders may be toxic, corrosive, or carcinogenic (e.g., heavy metal oxides, asbestos, silica). Handle powders in a fume hood; wear gloves, goggles, and dust mask/respirator. Dispose of residues per institutional hazardous waste rules.

Reagents

Powder samples finely ground to $<10 \mu\text{m}$ for random orientation with calibration standards (e.g., NIST SRM silicon), glass sample holders or low-background holders (Si zero-diffraction plates), adhesives or pastes (if mounting loose powders) and cleaning solvents (ethanol, isopropanol) for holders.

Procedure

1. Sample preparation

Dry sample if necessary to remove moisture, grind material to fine powder (<10 μm) to minimize preferred orientation and. Mount sample on a flat holder, ensuring a smooth, level surface. For sensitive materials: use sealed capillaries to prevent oxidation/hydration after hydration stoppage.

2. Measurement setup

Perform instrument alignment and calibration using standard (e.g., silicon). Set scan parameters: radiation: Cu $K\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$), 40 kV, 30 mA (typical), scan range: 5-80° 2θ (adjust depending on sample), step size: 0.01-0.02° 2θ , scan speed: 0.5-2°/min (slower for higher resolution). Place sample in stage, close protective doors, start scan and record diffraction pattern. Save raw data in instrument format and export as text (intensity vs. 2θ). Clean sample holder and workspace.

Reporting of result

Reports should include:

Sample information: ID, preparation method, particle size.

Instrument conditions: model, X-ray source, scan range, step size, scan speed.

Diffraction pattern: Plot intensity vs. 2θ , label major peaks, list detected phases with ICDD/PDF reference numbers. Match quality factors (R-factors or similarity index).

Quantitative results (if applicable): Phase fractions (Rietveld refinement or reference intensity ratio method), crystallite size and microstrain (using Scherrer equation or Williamson–Hall plot).

Uncertainties and limitations: preferred orientation, amorphous content, overlapping peaks.

Replicates and reproducibility: compare multiple scans if available.

Figure 6. X-ray diffractogram of uncarbonated sample

References

ASTM E1621 — *Standard Guide for X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Analysis of Crystalline Materials*.

Cullity, B. D., & Stock, S. R. — *Elements of X-ray Diffraction* (3rd Ed., Prentice Hall).

4.2 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Background and principle

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) measures the mass of a sample as a function of temperature and/or time while the sample is subjected to a controlled temperature program and controlled atmosphere (nitrogen, argon, synthetic air, oxygen). Mass changes occur because of processes such as desorption of moisture, evaporation of volatiles, thermal decomposition, oxidation, or reduction. The result is a TGA curve (mass vs. temperature/time) and often its derivative (DTG, rate of mass change), which allow determination of onset temperatures, decomposition steps, mass-loss percentages, and residual mass.

Figure 7. Thermogravimetric analyzer TA Instruments TGA 55

Special equipment

1. **Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA)** - choose model appropriate for required temperature range and sensitivity.
2. **Crucibles/pans** - materials: alumina (ceramic), platinum, or platinum–rhodium; choose chemically inert material for your sample and target atmosphere.
3. **Microbalance** - integrated to TGA or separated microbalance with mg sensitivity.
4. **Gas delivery system** - cylinder of purge gases (e.g., nitrogen, argon, synthetic air, oxygen), regulators, flow controllers/mass-flow controllers.
5. **Fume hood or exhausted enclosure** - to capture evolved gases if instrument isn't vented to a safe exhaust.
6. **Calibration weights and standard reference materials** for baseline checks and temperature calibration.
7. **Ancillary tools**- tweezers, micro-spatulas, balance for sample weighing, oven or desiccator for sample preconditioning.

Chemical safety

Personal protective equipment (PPE): lab coat, safety glasses, heat-resistant gloves for handling hot pans, appropriate respirator if toxic gases expected. Ensure instrument exhaust or fume hood can safely remove evolved gases; use gas traps or scrubbers if necessary.

Reagents

Purge gases: nitrogen (or argon) for inert atmosphere; synthetic air or oxygen for oxidative experiments. Use high-purity gas when required.

Calibration/reference materials: stable inorganic salts or manufacturer-provided calibration kits (e.g., alumina, calcium oxalate, standard polymers), and a certified temperature standard if available.

Crucibles: clean, appropriate material (alumina, Pt)

Cleaning solvents: isopropanol, acetone (use only on cooled pan), compatible components per manufacturer instructions.

Optional: desiccant or vacuum oven to dry hygroscopic samples prior to analysis.

Procedure

1. Sample preparation

Sample mass: typically 2-15 mg for powdered samples (common starting point \approx 5-10 mg). Adjust for sensitivity, volatile content, or if reaction is vigorous. Record exact mass to ± 0.01 mg or instrument resolution. Run duplicates/triplicates to assess variability. Grind or homogenize solid samples. Choose inert crucible (alumina for general use; Pt for corrosive samples if recommended). Clean crucible with isopropanol and tare on the TGA balance. Before the measurement dry sample in a vacuum oven or desiccator.

2. Measurement setup

Place sample in crucible (spread thinly to improve heat transfer). Record crucible ID. Program the temperature profile: initial isothermal hold (e.g., 25-50 °C hold for baseline stabilization, 5-10 min), heating ramp: e.g., 10 °C/min from ambient to final temperature. Typical final temperatures are 100–1000 °C depending on material, atmosphere can be inert (N₂, Ar) or oxidative (air, O₂). Typical range Gas flow rates is 40–60 mL/min, commonly 50 mL/min. When cooled to safe temperature, remove crucible with tongs, wash pan with isopropanol and store residues in an appropriate container for disposal.

Reporting of result

Suggested information to report, figures and tables

Sample identification: sample name, batch, physical form (powder, film), pretreatment (dried, desiccated), exact sample mass loaded (mg). Name the manufacturer and model of the TGA instrument and software version, used crucible/pan, temperature program and type of purge gas

Mass change data: absolute mass loss (mg) and relative (% of initial mass) for each step; give mass at start and at characteristic points.

Characteristic temperatures: T_{onset} (onset of mass loss) for each step, T_{max} (temperature of maximum mass-loss rate from DTG), and T_{end} or completion points. Describe how T_{onset} was determined (e.g., tangent method, 5% mass loss). Residual mass at final temperature end expressed as % of initial mass.

Plot: mass (%) vs. temperature (or time), DTG vs. temperature (on same x-axis) or separate panel.

Table: summary of mass-loss steps, T_{onset} , T_{max} , mass loss % for each step, residual %; instrument conditions.

Figure 8. Example of TGA data on clay

References

ASTM E1131 — *Standard Test Method for Compositional Analysis by Thermogravimetry*. (standard method describing reporting and practice).

Brown, M. E., & Gabbott, P. (eds.) - *Handbook of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry* (comprehensive reference on thermal techniques).

4.3 Determination of chloride content

Background and principle

Chloride ions in reinforced concrete are a major cause of corrosion of steel reinforcement, leading to structural deterioration. Determining the chloride content is essential for durability assessment, quality control, and service-life prediction of concrete structures.

The principle is based on acid extraction of chlorides from powdered concrete, followed by volumetric titration. Typically, chloride ions are titrated with a standard silver nitrate (AgNO_3) solution, using potentiometric detection (automatic titrator with Ag^+ -selective electrode). The titration end point corresponds to the sharp increase in potential once all chloride ions have precipitated as AgCl . The chloride concentration is expressed as % by mass of cement or by mass of concrete.

Figure 9. Automatic titrator with dosing unit for AgNO_3 solution and silver electrode indicator

Special equipment

1. **Automatic titrator** with: dosing unit for AgNO_3 solution, silver electrode (indicator), reference electrode
2. **Sample preparation tools:** core drill or grinder for concrete powder (depth-specific if needed), sieves (e.g., $<150\ \mu\text{m}$ fraction), analytical balance ($\pm 0.001\ \text{g}$)
3. **Glassware:** beakers, volumetric flasks, pipettes, funnels.
4. **Hot plate or digestion unit** for acid extraction.
5. **Filtration unit** (filter paper or vacuum filtration).

Chemical safety

Personal protective equipment: lab coat, safety glasses, nitrile gloves, a face shield and vapor respirator. Chemicals: nitric acid (HNO_3), hydrochloric acid (HCl), silver nitrate solution (AgNO_3) is an oxidizer, corrosive, and causes permanent skin stains (handle carefully with chemicals, avoid spills and wear protective gloves).

Dispose of AgNO_3 waste and acidic filtrates through approved hazardous-waste procedures (do not dispose in sink).

Reagents

Concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃), distilled/deionized water, standard silver nitrate (AgNO₃) solution (0.01–0.1 mol/L), standard sodium chloride (NaCl) solution (for calibration and checks), filter paper or filtration apparatus. Powder samples prepared from drill cores or crushed material.

Procedure

1. Sample preparation

Drill or grind concrete from required depth intervals and dry the powder at 105 ± 5 °C until constant mass. Sieve to <150 µm to ensure homogeneity. Weigh 1-2.0 g of dried sample into a beaker, add 50 mL distilled water to the beaker. Add 10 mL concentrated HNO₃ (to dissolve chloride salts and prevent interference). Heat gently on a hot plate for ~15 minutes without boiling. Cool sample suspension, filter into a volumetric flask, and dilute to a known volume (e.g., 100 mL).

2. Titration with automatic titrator

Pipette an aliquot (e.g., 25 mL) of filtrate into titration cell. Insert chloride electrode and start the titration program. The titrator will dispense AgNO₃ solution until the end point (sharp potential change) is detected. Record the volume of AgNO₃ used. Perform blank and standard solution titrations to confirm accuracy.

3. Calculation

Chloride concentration % by mass of concrete:

$$Cl^{-}(\%) = \frac{(V * C * 35,45)}{m} * 100$$

where:

V = volume of AgNO₃ used (L)

C = concentration of AgNO₃ (mol/L)

35,45 = molar mass of Cl (g/mol)

m = sample mass (g)

If reporting % chloride by mass of cement, apply the cement content of the concrete mix.

Reporting of result

Sample details: location, depth, collection method, drying method, sample mass used, acid concentration, dilution factor.

Titration parameters: titrant concentration, titration volume, electrode type, automatic titrator model, titrant volume (mL), blank corrections.

Calculated chloride content: % by mass of concrete (and optionally, % by mass of cement).

Remarks: anomalies during titration (e.g., drifting baseline, delayed endpoint).

References

ASTM C1152/C1152M — *Standard Test Method for Acid-Soluble Chloride in Mortar and Concrete.*

RILEM TC 178-TMC — *Chloride penetration into concrete.*

4.4 pH analysis

Background and principle

The pH of a solution is a measure of its hydrogen ion activity, defined as:

$$pH = -\log H^+$$

It indicates the acidity or alkalinity of a solution on a scale of 0–14. pH analysis is critical in chemistry, environmental monitoring, food science, concrete durability testing, and many industrial processes.

A pH meter with a glass electrode is commonly used. The electrode develops a potential that varies linearly with the logarithm of hydrogen ion activity, according to the Nernst equation. By calibrating against buffer solutions of known pH, the instrument converts measured potentials into accurate pH values.

Special equipment

pH meter with automatic temperature compensation (ATC) feature, glass pH electrode (combined glass + reference electrode), magnetic stirrer and stir bars (optional, for homogeneity), beakers.

Figure 10. SI Analytics LAB 645 pH meter with a glass electrode

Chemical safety

Personal protective equipment: lab coat, safety glasses, nitrile gloves, a face shield and vapor respirator. Strong acids and bases used in some sample extractions or calibrations.

Reagents

Standard buffer solutions (pH 4.00, 7.00, and 10.00 at 25 °C), distilled/deionized water (for rinsing electrode), sample solutions (water extracts, leachates, process solutions, etc.), electrode storage solution (typically 3 M KCl).

Procedure

1. Sample measurement

Rinse electrode with deionized water, then with a small portion of the sample. Place electrode in fresh aliquot of the sample. Stir gently to ensure homogeneity. Record pH when reading stabilizes. Measure and note sample temperature. Rinse electrode thoroughly between samples. Wash it after measurement with distilled water and dry, store electrode in electrode storage solution (3 M KCl).

Reporting of result

Reports should include:

1. **Sample ID and description** (origin, preparation method), **instrument detail**: pH meter model, electrode type, temperature compensation.
2. **Measured pH values**: raw and temperature-corrected (if applicable).

References

ASTM D1293 — *Standard Test Methods for pH of Water*.

IUPAC Recommendations (2002) — *Measurement of pH. Definition, Standards, and Procedures*.

4.5 Calcimetry measurement with de Bernard method

Background and principle

Calcimetry is a method used to determine the carbonate (CaCO_3) content in a solid sample, such as soil, limestone, cement, or other construction materials. The most common approach uses the Bernard calcimeter, which measures the volume of carbon dioxide (CO_2) gas released when carbonates react with an acid.

The reaction follows the principle:

When the sample reacts with hydrochloric acid (HCl), CO_2 is liberated and collected in a calibrated burette or gas collection tube. The volume of gas evolved is proportional to the carbonate content in the sample. By knowing the stoichiometry of the reaction and the conditions of temperature and pressure, the percentage of CaCO_3 can be calculated.

Special equipment

Bernard calcimeter consisting of: reaction flask, gas burette, leveling bottle, and connecting tubes, analytical balance (accuracy ± 0.001 g), thermometer for recording ambient temperature, barometer (for measuring atmospheric pressure, if gas volume correction is required), volumetric flasks, pipettes, and funnels for reagent preparation.

Figure 11. Bernard calcimeter

Chemical safety

Hydrochloric acid (HCl) is highly corrosive and produces irritating vapors, must be handled in a fume hood while wearing safety goggles, gloves, and a lab coat. CO_2 gas is non-toxic but can displace oxygen in confined spaces; ensure adequate ventilation. Neutralize acidic residues with sodium bicarbonate before disposal. Dispose of liquid wastes and reaction residues according to institutional and environmental regulations.

Reagents

Hydrochloric acid (HCl), 1:4 dilution (approximately 25% v/v concentrated HCl in distilled water), distilled or deionized water for cleaning and dilutions, calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) analytical grade for calibration or reference tests, indicator dye (optional) for visual monitoring of reaction progress.

Procedure

1. Preparation of apparatus

Ensure the Bernard calcimeter is clean, dry, and airtight. Fill the leveling bottle and burette with water or acid-saturated solution to avoid gas dissolution. Check for air leaks in the system by gently pressurizing it. Accurately weigh **0.5–2.0 g** of finely ground, dried sample using an analytical balance. Transfer the sample into the reaction flask of the calcimeter.

2. Reaction and gas measurement

Add a known volume of diluted HCl into the side arm or reservoir of the apparatus without immediate contact with the sample. Seal the system and carefully allow the acid to flow into the reaction flask to initiate the reaction. The carbonate reacts with acid, releasing CO₂ gas that is collected in the burette. Wait until gas evolution ceases (typically 5–10 minutes). Record the **volume of CO₂ gas** collected, as well as the ambient temperature and pressure.

3. Calculation

The carbonate content is calculated from the measured CO₂ volume using the ideal gas law and the known stoichiometric relationship between CaCO₃ and CO₂.

Formula for carbon content calculation:

$$\% \text{CaCO}_3 = \frac{V * (P - P_w) * 100 * Mr_{\text{CaCO}_3}}{22.4 * T * m * Mr_{\text{CO}_2}}$$

where:

V = volume of CO₂ (mL)

P = atmospheric pressure (mmHg)

P_w = water vapor pressure (mmHg)

T = temperature (K)

m = sample mass (g)

Mr_{CaCO₃} = 100.09 g/mol

Mr_{CO₂} = 44.01 g/mol

Reporting of result

The report should include the following: sample mass and test conditions (temperature, pressure), volume of CO₂ evolved and any corrections applied for temperature or pressure. Calculated carbonate (CaCO₃) content, expressed as % by mass. Replicate measurements and standard deviation (if applicable), observations such as reaction rate, residual solids, or unusual behavior during gas evolution.

References

HRN EN ISO 10693:2014 — *Soil quality — Determination of carbonate content — Volumetric method.*

5 PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

5.1 Mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP)

Background and principle

Mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP) is a technique used to determine pore size distribution, pore volume, porosity, and bulk density of solid materials. The principle is based on the non-wetting nature of mercury: it does not spontaneously penetrate pores due to its high surface tension and contact angle with most solids. Applying external pressure forces mercury into the pores.

According to the equation:

$$r = -\frac{2\gamma \cos\theta}{P}$$

where r is pore radius, γ is the surface tension of mercury, θ is the contact angle, and P is the applied pressure. Measuring the intruded volume at different pressures gives the pore size distribution over the range ~ 3 nm to $1000 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 12. Mercury intrusion porosimeter with low-pressure and high-pressure unit

Special equipment

1. **Mercury intrusion porosimeter** (e.g., AutoPore, Pascal, or similar models) with:
 - Low-pressure unit (vacuum to ~ 0.2 MPa) for larger pores
 - High-pressure unit (up to 200–400 MPa) for fine pores
2. **Sample holders/penetrometers:** glass or metal dilatometers designed for the porosimeter.
3. **Analytical balance:** ± 0.1 mg precision.
4. **Fume hood with mercury vapor filter** (if instrument exhaust is not directly vented).

5. **Spill trays and mercury spill kit:** sulfur powder/ amalgamation powder/ mercury absorbing powder, water spray bottle, latex/ nitrile gloves, shoe coverings, plastic scoop, resistant disposal bag/ container.
6. **Mercury Vacuum cleaner:** specifically designed to safely collect and retain liquid mercury spills and granular compounds while eliminating toxic vapours.
7. **Personal protective equipment (PPE):** lab coat, safety glasses, nitrile gloves, face shield and mercury vapor respirator, shoe coverings.

Chemical safety

Mercury is highly toxic via vapor inhalation, ingestion, or skin absorption. All handling of mercury must be done in a dedicated area with secondary containment and spill response materials ready. Use only properly calibrated, closed porosimeter systems. Never handle mercury in open vessels.

If a spill occurs: evacuate area, use a mercury spill kit (sulfur powder, amalgamation powder, or commercial absorbent), and dispose of contaminated material as hazardous waste. Waste mercury and contaminated glassware must be collected in sealed, labeled containers and disposed through approved hazardous-waste channels.

Avoid placing porous samples containing volatile organics, water, or reactive compounds (e.g., carbides, alkali metals) in the instrument, as they can react with mercury or cause dangerous pressure changes.

Figure 13. Pump for mercury spills and protection materials under the instrument

Reagents

High-purity mercury ($\geq 99.99\%$), supplied in sealed dark bottles.

Cleaning solvents: acetone, ethanol, water, special detergent for penetrometers.

Desiccant or vacuum drying oven (to pre-dry samples).

Reference materials for instrument calibration (manufacturer-provided).

Inert gases (e.g., nitrogen) for drying and purging.

Procedure

1. Sample preparation

Dry samples at 30-120 °C (or appropriate for material stability) under vacuum or in an oven to remove adsorbed water/volatiles. Cool samples in a desiccator. Weigh accurately 1-2 g (± 0.1 mg). Record initial sample mass and mass of sample loaded penetrometer.

2. Measurement steps setup

Check mercury reservoir levels and ensure no leaks. Load weighted sample in penetrometer, assemble cover and penetrometer with O-ring properly sealed with high resistant pressure grease (ensure uniform packing without voids or fractures). Place sample loaded penetrometer in the low-pressure chamber. Program the measurement profile: pressure range, equilibrium times, intrusion/extrusion cycle details, record the sample mass of penetrometer before and after low- pressure measurement. During low-pressure intrusion (up to ~ 200 kPa) mercury fills macropores (>50 μm). Record volume of mercury by measuring sample and mercury loaded penetrometer. Afterwards, during high-pressure intrusion (up to 200–400 MPa) mercury intrudes progressively into smaller pores (down to ~ 3 nm). Instrument records applied pressure and intruded volume continuously.

4. Post-run handling

After full run, carefully remove penetrometer from the instrument and collect mercury and sample residues for hazardous-waste disposal (mercury-contaminated). Wash penetrometer with special detergent, rinse with ethanol and dry thoroughly.

Reporting of result

Reports should include:

Sample details: ID, preparation method, dry sample mass.

Instrument conditions: model, maximum pressure, contact angle used (commonly 130°), mercury surface tension assumed (485 dyn/cm at 25 °C), pressure range, equilibrium times, intrusion/extrusion cycle details.

Results: Pore size distribution curve ($dV/d\log D$ vs. pore diameter), cumulative intrusion volume vs. pore diameter, total pore volume (cm^3/g), apparent (skeletal and bulk) density, porosity (%), median pore diameter (by volume).

References

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5.2 Blaine analysis

Background and principle

The Blaine air permeability method is widely used to determine the fineness of cement in terms of its specific surface area (cm^2/g). The principle is based on measuring the time required for a fixed volume of air to flow through a compacted bed of cement powder under a given pressure difference. According to Darcy's law, the flow resistance is related to the surface area of particles. A calibrated reference cement is used to convert measured flow times into specific surface area.

Figure 14. Blaine air permeability apparatus UTEST Schneider Harmony

Special equipment

1. **Blaine air permeability apparatus**, consisting of:
 - Permeability cell (internal diameter ~ 12.5 mm, height ~ 50 mm).
 - U-tube manometer with scale (for pressure drop measurement).
 - Perforated disc, filter paper, plunger, and clamp set.
2. **Balance** with ± 0.001 g accuracy.
3. **Stopwatch** with ± 0.1 s accuracy.
4. **Thermometer** (± 0.5 °C) since air viscosity depends on temperature.
5. **Calibrated reference cement** (specific surface area certified).
6. **Desiccator or sealed container** to prevent cement moisture absorption.

Chemical safety

Personal protective equipment (PPE): lab coat, safety glasses, gloves, appropriate dust mask or respirator in poorly ventilated areas. Handle glass U-tube carefully to avoid breakage. Dispose sample powder residues according to institutional waste guidelines (non-hazardous, but avoid releasing dust to environment).

Reagents

Test sample dried, free of lumps.

Calibrated reference sample (with known specific surface area).

Filter papers/discs for permeability cell, spatula.

Cleaning supplies: brushes, compressed air, ethanol for manometer cleaning if necessary.

Procedure

1. Preparation

Dry sample at 105 ± 5 °C for 1 hour; cool in desiccator. Assemble permeability cell with a filter paper disc at the bottom. Weigh a specific mass of sample (typically ~2.8 g, depending on sample density) to fill the cell. Place sample into cell in small increments and compact using the plunger to obtain a uniform packing height (usually 15 ± 0.5 mm). Place filter paper and perforated disc on top. Record packed volume and mass to determine bed porosity ($\sim 0.50 \pm 0.01$).

2. Measurement

Connect the cell to the Blaine apparatus (U-tube manometer filled with liquid). Adjust air pressure so that the liquid meniscus in the U-tube is at the upper mark. Release the air and start the stopwatch when meniscus passes the upper mark. Stop timing when meniscus reaches the lower mark. Record flow time (t) in seconds.

3. Calibration and calculation

Repeat procedure with reference sample under identical conditions.

Reporting of result

Sample details: type of cement, batch, preparation method, dry mass used.

Apparatus details: Blaine model, calibration date, reference cement used.

Test conditions: bed porosity, packed height, ambient temperature (°C), calculated specific surface area (cm^2/g).

Flow times: for both sample and reference (average of 3-4 runs, reject outliers).

Remarks: deviations from standard procedure, abnormal flow behavior, or clogging.

References

EN 196-6 Methods of testing cement -- Part 6: Determination of fineness

ASTM C204 Standard Test Methods for Fineness of Hydraulic Cement by Air-Permeability Apparatus

5.3 Calorimetry

Calorimetry is used to measure the heat of hydration of cementitious materials. The heat released during hydration reflects the rate and extent of reaction between cement (or supplementary cementitious materials, SCMs) and water. By recording heat flow over time with an isothermal calorimeter, hydration kinetics (induction, acceleration, and deceleration stages) can be evaluated.

5.3.1 Reactivity test (R3 test)

Background and principle

The R3 test (RILEM TC 267-TRM (2017)) provides a standardized measure of pozzolanic and latent hydraulic reactivity of SCMs. It evaluates their reactivity in a simplified reference system ($\text{Ca(OH)}_2 + \text{KOH} + \text{CaSO}_4$ solution, known as “R3 solution”) rather than in full cement paste. Reactivity is quantified either by calorimetry (heat release in 7 days) or by measuring bound water and chemically combined Ca(OH)_2 . This test allows direct comparison of different SCMs under identical conditions.

Figure 15. Isothermal conduction calorimeter TAM AIR

Special equipment

Isothermal conduction calorimeter (for calorimetry and R3), analytical balance (± 0.001 g), glass vials with caps (suitable for calorimeter ampoules). Mixing setup and oven (105 °C) (for bound water determination in R3).

Chemical safety

Personal protective equipment: lab coat, safety glasses, nitrile gloves, a face shield and vapor respirator. Dispose of waste solutions in accordance with institutional hazardous-waste protocols (especially high-pH solutions).

Reagents

Deionized water, calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2), potassium hydroxide (KOH), analytical grade, calcium sulfate dihydrate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) (fly ash, slag, silica fume, etc.) or ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) for reference calorimetry.

Procedure

The test method requires two different samples: the test sample and the reference sample.

The reference sample is generally deionized water or quartz sand. The mass of reference depends on the total heat capacity of the test sample and is calculated through the following formula:

$$m_r = \frac{m_c c_c + m_w c_w}{c_r}$$

Table 3 Heat capacity from main components used in cement calorimetry.

Material	Heat capacity (Jg-1K-1)
Cement	0.8
Water	4.18
Quartz	0.75

The reference sample is loaded inside the channels generally **before the initial baseline** and (if needed) removed at the end of the final baseline. **The initial baseline should be recorded min. 4 h before testing** (preferably 24 h) and recorded for **the same duration after** the samples have been removed.

The test sample may be prepared at the end of the initial baseline period.

The calorimeter always shows a certain response, i.e., a signal. Before starting a new experiment, the signals from all channels should be approximately 0 mW. If not so, before starting the experiment, it is necessary to set all signals to zero by clicking the icon on the toolbar before start of the new experiment. The baseline measurement will begin when the signal is stable (which may take several hours) and should not be skipped.

All constituents shall be conditioned to a temperature as close as possible to the testing temperature. A stable temperature of **20 ± 0.5 °C** shall be maintained for standard calorimetry measurements, and **40 ± 0.5 °C** for the **R3 test**. This can be achieved by placing the constituents in an oven 24 h before test.

The mixing is performed in a high-shear mixer at **1600 ± 50 rpm for 2 minutes** to ensure a homogeneous paste. The paste should then be **immediately cast into a glass vial**. Each sample, immediately after casting, must be inserted into the designated calorimeter channel, and the experiment should be started for that specific channel (maximum 4 min after start of mixing).

1. Calorimetry (cement paste or mortar)

Prepare paste with required water-to-binder ratio (typically 0.40). Weigh ~5 g binder into calorimeter vial. Add water, mix quickly and homogenize. The mixing procedure Place vial into isothermal calorimeter immediately. Record heat flow for 1–7 days.

2. R3 test (solution-based reactivity)

Prepare R3 solution day before by mixing: 0.20 g Ca(OH)₂, 0.20 g KOH, 0.50 g CaSO₄·2H₂O dissolved in 100 g deionized water and place it (together with powdered materials) in an oven to stabilize the temperature at **40 ± 0.5 °C**. Mix SCM sample with R3 solution at **solution/SCM = 2.0 by mass**. Place the mixture (15 g) into calorimeter vial. Start calorimetry and record heat release for 7 days.

After 7 days, filter residue, dry at 105 °C, and determine **bound water** and **Ca(OH)₂ consumption** (via thermogravimetry or chemical analysis).

Reporting of result

Calorimetry: heat flow curve (W/g vs. time), cumulative heat release (J/g at 1 day, 3 days, 7 days) and comparison between different binders or SCM blends.

R3 test: cumulative heat release in 7 days (J/g SCM), bound water content (% by mass), Ca(OH)₂ consumption (if determined).

Reports should include: sample ID and type (cement, SCM), mixing proportions and water/binder ratio, calorimeter model and test temperature.

The cumulative heat release measured by the R3 test over 7 days is presented in **Figure 16**. The results provide insight into the reactivity of the selected uncarbonated SCMs, simulating early-age hydration conditions.

Figure 16. R3 results of raw uncarbonated materials

References

RILEM TC 267-TRM (2017). *Recommendation for the R3 test method to evaluate the pozzolanic reactivity of supplementary cementitious materials.*

ASTM C1702 — *Standard Test Method for Measurement of Heat of Hydration of Hydraulic Cementitious Materials Using Isothermal Conduction Calorimetry.*

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